

Perceived Risk Act as an Antecedent Towards the Usage of Digital Payment System

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Abstract

India is a nation of diversity with unity. One such example is digital payment system, but every good action is backed by a nuisance action i.e. Online Payment Fraud. The fraud brings in the concept of risk in the mindset of users. Thus, the study focusses on the perceived risk which acts as a barrier to use the digital payment system. The study also focuses on the impact of the elements of perceived risk (financial risk, security risk, performance risk and social risk) and the demographic variables (age and gender) on perceived risk and eventually impacting the intention to use digital payment system. The findings suggested that increase in number of fraud cases have made the perceived risk strong component for the intention to use digital payment system. The results shows that risk elements and demographic variables were significantly impacting the perceived risk that was restricting the users to use digital payment system. The curbing down of frauds and enhancing the people knowledge about the digital payment system can curtail the perceived risk concept from the mindset of users.

Keywords: *Perceived Risk, Digital Payment System, Financial Risk, Security Risk, Fraud.*

JEL Classification: *G400, G410.*

1. Introduction

India is a vast country with varied culture and heritage. The diversity in its demography makes it an impacting nation in the world. Even if its diverse it is united which helps the nation to grow stronger. One such example of unity is Digital Economy. Digital Economy in India is the starting of the digital revolution, by which government can provide service access to the citizens electronically (Rani, 2021). In order to make India 'Digital India' the Government of India brought the term demonetization in November 2016 that made the country use Digital Payment System for day-to-day transactions. Indian economy after going digital became a sustainable economy.

The major role of making India a digital economy goes to Digital payment system. After the implementation of demonetization people were compelled to use digital payment methods, however after COVID-19 struck it was used in full swing. Badak et al,2023 states that the digital payment system became common that easily was due to the ease of transferring money from one person to another person's account. Demonetization and COVID-19 just act as the catalyst to make the process sooner as well as easier. However, Sivathanu, 2017 have stated

that initially people were inclined towards cash payment method over Digital payment System as they were having a hitch to use it. People had the perception that while using digital payment system it is possible that transaction could fail, phishing or vishing of account might happen, bank account details might be leaked to some other fellow. (Chandrasekaran & Narayanan, 2019) have suggested that if digital payment system has its advantage, then it also has few disadvantages from which identity theft, financial loss was most common.

Despite all these challenges people became habituated to use digital payment system after the occurrence COVID-19 in 2020. According to National Payment Corporation of India (NPCI) data set given initially people were not using digital payment system because of lockdown. But people very soon understood the benefit of using digital payment system. Digital payment system usage means payment is cashless, faceless and paperless. Badak et al 2023, have also mentioned that digital payment system was safer as well as convenient which ultimately reflected in the increase in usage of it by the customers.

Digital payment system is helping the Government of India to realize the dream of Digital India to some extent. Vally & Divya, 2018 have observed that customer's adoption of digital payment system has enhanced the banks' performance as well as made the society cashless. In order to promote the new payment method, the government took the initiative to make it safe and easy to use so as to win the trust of customers and convince them to transact money via digital mode only. For this purpose, government brought in the concept of e-governance. E-governance umbrella takes in lots of features which safeguards the customers from cyber frauds. This umbrella stands on nine pillars which helps the government in tightening the cyber security.

Previously, the digital payment methods were dependent on internet connectivity but now it has spread its wings making itself free from its limitation. Reserve Bank of India (RBI) & NPCI collaborative approach to reach everyone and make digital payment system a success enabled the person to transfer the money via mobile service also.

Digital payment system has crossed the stage of acceptance in the market. According to PwC Report 2022, India is the leading country in terms of Digital Payment System usage however it also has provided the room for Online Payment Frauds. As per RBI annual report, 2024, the number of online payment frauds have increased from the previous year. This increment in fraudulent cases of digital payment system is making customer think twice before its usage. Pandey, 2022 have supported the above stated fact that usage of digital payment may get impacted by the increase of cyber frauds as it is killing the goodwill of Digital payment system in the market. In order to understand the perceived risk association with the acceptance level of digital payment system technology acceptance model was used.

Technology Acceptance Model given by Fred Davis in 1989 states that actual usage of any new Technology is impacted by the behavioural intention to use it. This behavioural intention was influenced by perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of that new technology. However, Venkatesh & Davis, 2000 came up with a theory that both perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness have antecedents that affect the behavioural intention to use the new technology. Voluntariness, Subjective norm, Job relevance, Result Demonstrability, etc. were few of the antecedents of them.

Further researches done by researchers like Sobti, 2019 have stated that perceived risk is also associated with the behavioural intention to use digital payment systems. On the same mark Shrivastava et al, 2019 have also shown the impact of perceived risk, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on the behavioural intention of bank's customers to use green banking products and services (mobile banking, internet banking, etc.).

Thus, the current research focuses on the impact of perceived risk on behavioural intention to use digital payment systems. Along With this the research strives to know perceived risk's elements which are affecting the perceived risk in customers and eventually affecting the behavioural intention to use digital payment systems. The study also emphasizes the importance of gender and age role in affecting the perceived risk.

The research is divided into five parts where first part deals with the brief introduction, second speaks about the past studies and hypothesis development in Theoretical Background and Hypothesis Development, third shows the methodology used for achieving the solutions to concerns raised in the introduction, fourth showcases the results obtained in findings and discussion and last part concludes the paper with conclusion and policy implications.

2. Theoretical Background and Hypothesis Development

In order to recognize the behavioural intention of users towards the new technology various studies have been done. Technology Acceptance Model given by Fred Davis, 1989, the successor of the theory of reasoned action given by Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975 is widely used. Theory of reasoned action focused on the behavioural intention of an individual which was affected by factors like subjective norm and attitude (Trafimow, 2009).

For analysing the theory of reasoned action is considered as one of the best theories, however technology acceptance model is more prominent than the previous theories. Davis, 1993, focuses on the causal relationship between system design features, perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, attitude towards using and actual usage behaviour. However, in 2000 Davis along with Venkatesh gave new technology acceptance model. Now the attitude construct was removed and perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness had few antecedents that influenced them and eventually the behavioural intention of an individual to use that new technology. Researchers like Cunningham et al (2005), Featherman and Pavlov (2002), Lee (2009). Zhao et al (2008) have emphasized the third construct of perceived risk for the digital payment system acceptance among its user's acceptance.

2.1 Behavioural intention (Intention to use Digital Payment System)

Ajzen & Fishbein 1975, behavioural intention is the readiness to perform a certain behaviour. Venkatesh 2003 stated that behavioural intention as the desire to perform any action. Venkatesh & Davis 2000 proposed that intention to use any new system is influenced by perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, the new model focussed on the external stimulus and cognitive response for the actual behaviour to occur. The external stimulus drives the perceived ease of use and cognitive construct is the perceived usefulness which affects the intention ultimately intention to use influences the action of an individual. Thus, the hypothesis can be formed as:

H₁: There is a positive relationship between Behavioural intention and Actual Usage.

2.1.1 Perceived Risk

It may be understood as the persons' assessment of degree of the uncertainty associated to a specific product or service usage would fail to give the favourable outcome. Reepu & Arora, 2022 refers perceived risk as the impacting influences towards the intention to use online banking. Budhi et al (2022) states that perceived risk has direct influence on the intention to use online banking. Shrivastava et al (2019) have also stated perceived risk as the main construct to impact the intention to use. Thus, the hypothesis could be formed as

H₂: Perceived risk has a negative relationship with behavioural intention to use.

Bazgosha et al (2012) have identified five elements of perceived risk which are there in the mind of any person namely security risk, financial risk, time risk, psychological risk, social risk. Cunningham et al (2005) have introduced two new elements to the above performance risk and physical risk. Zhao et al (2008) have introduced other element i.e. privacy risk that impacts the intention to use digital payment system.

For carrying out the study, it focusses on four elements (Financial risk, Security risk, Performance risk and social risk) risks that eventually impacts the intention to use the digital payment system.

2.1.1.1 Financial risk

The chances of losing money due to the usage of new technology (digital payment system). E-banking using customers are concerned about the potential frauds of losing their money they are exposed while performing a transaction. Hanafizadeh et al, 2012 have pointed out customers are concerned about the human errors they could make during the transaction like entering wrong digits for transacting the money or the details of the person or if continuous errors were made, they would lose the control of their personal account. Thus, the hypothesis formulated here is:

H₃: Perceived risk is significantly impacted by financial risk.

2.1.1.2 Security risk

Arora & Kaur, 2018 defined the security risk as the potential loss of control over personal information. It is the core hindrance while using the e-banking services. The users are anxious about the transaction of money from their account or about their personal information would be used or seen by others without their permission. Littler & Melanthiou, 2006, the cases of frauds provide the evidence for this like hacking of websites, internet theft. Bazgosha et al 2012, states that the loss of money leads to loss of trust also violates that users' privacy. The hypothesis drafted here is as follows:

H₄: Perceived risk is significantly impacted by the security risk.

2.1.1.3 Performance risk

It could also be said as the functional risk as it concerns customers ideology towards the function of the product or services. Hanafizadeh et al 2012, customers are most concerned about the performance of the digital payment system (e-banking). The customers have the issue of malfunctioning of the system like server problems, maintenance of the website or the app, troubleshooting of the activities, the system might fail to deliver the required result on time. Reepu & Arora, 2022, have stated that performance risk does damage the online banking environment due to bank failure or their weaknesses. Featherman & Pavlov, 2002 study was also found in line with the above studies. The hypothesis framed here is:

H₅: Perceived risk is significantly impacted by the performance risk.

2.1.1.4 Social risk

It could be termed as reputational risk. The risk which generated from the pessimistic viewpoint of others (family, friends or peers). The customers do follow a new technology due to social influence (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000) but if the outcome of the usage of technology is unfavourable then it impacts the users' mindset. Arora & Kaur; 2018, Lee; 2009, Littler & Melanthiou; 2006, studies done by them suggest that potential loss of status of an individual in its individual's societal group may occur due to errors while performing the transaction or due to frauds. Thus, the hypothesis formed here is:

H₆: Perceived risk is significantly impacted by the social risk.

2.1.1.5 Demographic variable (Age)

Sobti, 2019 have found that age of customers using digital payment system was having moderating yet impacting relationship with the perceived risk. Singh & Sharma, 2023 followed the pitch and found that age of consumers' during Pandemic was significantly impacting the perceived risk which eventually impacted the behavioural intention to use digital payment system. Thus, the hypothesis formed for the above stated fact is:

H₇: Age is significantly related to the perceived risk.

2.1.1.6 Demographic variable (Gender)

People from different demographic background have different level of perceived risk in their mind for using the digital payment system. Undale, 2021 have revealed that females are more concerned about the e-wallet security rather than male customers. As Joshi & Chawla, 2024 have also supported the fact that gender has an impacting relationship with trust and perceived security. Yadav et al, 2024 on the same pitch said that gender of customers does have an impact on the perceived risk as well as on the perceived risk elements for the usage of mobile payment system. Thus, the hypothesis formulated is:

H₈: Gender is significantly related to the perceived risk

3. Data & Methodology

This section deals with the data collected as well as used, empirical model used in the study.

3.1 Data

The data collected and used for the study is primary in nature. Within Indore city there were total 184 cases of Online payment Frauds which increased from 130 from last year. Total number of registered FIRs in 2023 was 50 which reduced to only 30 FIRs. Therefore, the 100 respondents chosen for the study from Indore city in particular who have been the victim of the online payment fraud whether they have registered or unregistered the complaint against the fraud or not. The respondents were given self-structured questionnaire which consists of 44 questions consisting of two questions of demographic variables, two about online payment frauds and 40 questions related to the intention of using digital payment system in the future. The questions related to demography consists of age group (18-30, 31-45,46-60, 60 & above) and gender (male and female). The 40 questions related to intention to use digital payment system are recorded on 5-point Likert scale, where 5 denotes Strongly Agree and 1 means Strongly Disagree.

3.2 Variables

Venkatesh & Davis, 2000; 1996 have state that all antecedents have its own impact on the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. Reepu & Arora, 2022 study is line with it stating the antecedents of perceived risk is impacting perceived risk which eventually affects the intention to use. Thus, the dependent variable would be behavioural intention to use digital payment system for the first research concern. Further, perceived risk would be acting as the dependent variables for knowing the impact of antecedents on the perceived risk and the demographic variables. For the view of dependent variables and independent variables refer to Table 1.

Cunningham et al; 2005, Moradi et al; 2012, Fadre et al; 2016 have used the multiple variable regression model for analysing the risk. Shrivastava et al, 2019 have used both multiple variable regression and linear probability model to analyse the risk' impact on actual behaviour.

Table 1: Variables used in the model

<u>Equation</u>	<u>Dependent Variable</u>	<u>Independent Variable</u>	<u>Supporting Reviews</u>
1	Actual Usage (AU)	Behavioural Intention (BI)	Davis, 1989, Sobti (2019) Shrivastava et al (2019), Sivathanu (2017)
2	Behavioural Intention (BI)	Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)	Davis, 1989, Venkatesh & Davis, 1996, Chawla & Joshi (2019), Haritha (2022), Sandhu et al (2023)
		Perceived Usefulness (PU)	Davis, 1989, Venkatesh & Davis, 2000, Chawla & Joshi (2019), Haritha (2022), Vimal et al (2023)
		Perceived Risk (PR)	Sinha et al (2024), Sinha et al (2019), Shrivastava et al (2019)
3	Perceived Risk (PR)	Financial Risk	Zhao et al (2011), Manoranjan et al (2012), Moradi et al (2012)
		Security Risk	Zhao et al (2011), Moradi et al (2012), Fadre et al (2016)
		Performance Risk	Zhao et al (2011), Moradi et al (2012), Featherman & Pavlov (2002)
		Social Risk	Zhao et al (2011), Moradi et al (2012), Roy et al (2016)
4	Perceived Risk (PR)	Age	Singh & Sharma (2023), Sobti (2019)
		Gender	Manrai et al (2021), Yadav et al (2024)

Based on the study of Reepu & Arora; 2022, Joshi & Chawla;2024 the following empirical model were formed

Equation 1:

$$AU_i = \lambda_0 + \lambda_1 BI_i + u_i$$

Here Actual usage (AU) is dependent on the behavioural intention (BI) to use digital payment system. Actual Usage is a binary variable having value of 0 and 1 only, where 1 means using digital payment system and 0 means not using digital payment system.

Equation 2:

$$BI_i = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 PEOU_i + \gamma_2 PU_i + \gamma_3 PR_i + u_i$$

Here, Behavioural intention (BI) is dependent on the perceived ease of use (PEOU) and perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived risk (PR).

Equation 3:

$$PR_i = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \text{Fin R}_i + \alpha_2 \text{Sec R}_i + \alpha_3 \text{Perf R}_i + \alpha_4 \text{Soc R}_i + u_i$$

Here, Perceived Risk (PR) is dependent on the antecedents Financial Risk (Fin R), Security Risk (Sec R), Performance Risk (Perf R), Social Risk (Soc R).

Equation 4:

$$PR_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + u_i$$

Here, Perceived Risk (PR) is dependent on the demographic variable age (X_{1i}) and gender (X_{2i}).

Model for Perceived Risk Antecedents with the help of Technology Acceptance Model

4. Findings & Discussion

From the table given below reliability of the questionnaire can be seen. The value of Cronbach alpha test was 0.838 which is considered as good fit for the reliability of the data set available. The test was carried out on IBM SPSS 28.

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.835	.838	40

From the result given below in Table 3 it is evident that the victims are having hitch in using but still they are using the digital payment system. The result highlights the importance of perceived risk that has negative and significant impact on the behavioural intention to use digital payment system with t-value 2.8798 which is higher than the tabulated value and found significant at 1% level of significance. Khan & Abideen (2023) have also found the impact of perceived risk on the behavioural intention to use digital wallet. The behavioural intention to use internet banking is negatively impacted by perceived risk as stated by Kesharwani & Bisht, 2011. Thus, the hypothesis (H₂) is accepted that perceived risk has a negative impact on the behavioural intention to use.

Table 3: Result for Equation 2

Dependent Variable: Behavioural Intention			
Independent Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-stat
Intercept	1.4931	1.2120	1.2319
Perceived Ease of Use	0.4313*	0.2068	2.0846
Perceived Usefulness	0.3266*	0.1657	1.9705
Perceived Risk	-0.6192*	0.2150	-2.8789

* Found significant at 5% level of significance.

Perceived risk elements financial risk, security risk, performance risk and social risk impacts the perceived risk. From the result given below in Table 4 the t-value of financial risk obtained is 2.4116 which is higher than that of tabulated value at 5% level of significance. The security risk t- value is 2.1212 which is again found significant at 5% level of significance. The third driving variable is performance risk has the t- value of 2.0102 which is found significant at 5% level of significance and the least impacting is the social risk with t-value as 2.3087 which is significant at 5% level of significance. Thus, from the results obtained the following hypotheses are being accepted.

H₃: Perceived risk is significantly impacted by financial risk.

H₄: Perceived risk is significantly impacted by security risk.

H₅: Perceived risk is significantly impacted by performance risk.

H₆: Perceived risk is significantly impacted by social risk.

The study’s results are in line with the results of Zhao et al; 2008, Reepu & Arora, 2012. These studies also suggested that the elements of perceived risk have an impact on perceived risk which eventually impacts the behavioural intention.

Table 4: Result for Equation 3			
Dependent Variable: Perceived Risk			
Independent Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-stat
Intercept	2.6825	1.3642	1.9663
Financial Risk	0.6955*	0.2883	2.4116
Security Risk	0.4113*	0.2046	2.0102
Performance Risk	0.5098*	0.2403	2.1212
Social Risk	0.2976*	0.1289	2.3087
* Found significant at 5% level of significance.			

The Table 5 shows that perceived risk is having the impact of the two demographic variables (age and gender). Age and gender have an impact on perceived risk as t-value scored are 1.9947

and 2.4768 respectively which is significant at 5% level of significance. Hence the following hypotheses are accepted.

H₇: Age is significantly related to the perceived risk.

H₈: Gender is significantly related to the perceived risk.

Yadav et al (2024) have suggested that women are more risk averse than men. Undale et al (2021) have also revealed that e-wallets have male users than the female. Singh & Sharma (2023) stated that perceived COVID risk was impacted by the age of the users. Sobti (2019) suggested that younger generation were more inclined towards the usage of mobile payment services as compared to the older generation because of their risk appetite.

Table 5: Result for Equation 4			
Dependent Variable: Perceived Risk			
Independent Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-stat
Intercept	3.5521	0.3221	11.02801
Age	0.1412*	0.0708	1.9947
Gender	0.4368*	0.1763	2.4768
* Found significant at 5% level of significance.			

The Table 6 shows that Actual usage of Digital Payment System by victims would be happening if they have behavioural intention to use it. The t-value obtained is 2.2034 which is higher than the tabulated value, thus the hypothesis (H₁) is accepted that there is a positive relationship between actual usage and behavioural intention to use digital payment system.

Table 6: Result for Equation 1			
	Dependent Variable: Actual Usage		
Independent Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-stat
Intercept	0.3542	0.4106	0.8626
Behavioural Intention to Use	0.2660*	0.1207	2.2034

* Found significant at 5% level of significance.

5. Conclusion & Policy Implications

The focus of the study is on the perceived risk which is acting as a potential influencer for the intention to use digital payment system. From the results obtained the online payment frauds' victim are losing the trust in the digital payment system as they got scammed and lost their hard earn money. This has sown the seed of perceptual risk in their mind. It is clearly evident that now the people are perceiving risk more rather than perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. For the better understanding of the mindset the study delved into the elements of the perceived risk; financial risk, security risk, performance risk and social risk. And sadly, all the risk elements were found impacting the perceived risk of and individual. In the last age and gender of the individual was also considered, the results showed that both age and gender had an impact on the behavioural intention to use digital payment due to perceived risk.

The country is known for its highest usage of digital payment system in the world. Others wish to copy this practice from India. The way chosen for transacting money may be appealing, tech friendly, eco- friendly and available to everyone 24 by 7 but the obstacle which ensued was online payment fraud. The cyber fraudsters are well aware about the digital payment system but people are not that much aware about the digital payment system features. Kurian, 2022 have also stated that if people are fully aware about the potential as well as the features of digital payment system then the country could very soon achieve its target of cashless society. Only due to this lack of knowledge people are prone to risk associated with digital payment system. Fraudsters have the full knowledge use this as their weapon and lure the people into their traps of frauds. This became the reason for arising of perceived risk which is compelling an individual to restrict the usage of digital payment system.

Pandey, 2022 have also suggested that reduction in the online payment fraud could increase the usage of digital payment system. Thus, the government initiative to enhance the awareness level of the users of the digital payment system could curb down the number of the frauds. The emphasis should be on the building of knowledge as well as on trust so as to make people more

inclined to register the fraudulent cases to the authority if fraud occurs. The users should have the trust that they would get their lost money, this would surely curb cyber payment frauds. The things would surely become smoother if the rough patches like digital payment system's literacy ignorance be filled with the knowledge.

References

Ajzen, I. (1988). *Attitudes, personality, and behaviour*. Chicago: Dorsey.

Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behaviour. *Organizational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179–211.

Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1980). *Understanding attitudes and predicting social behaviour*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall

Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (2005). The influence of attitudes on behaviour. In D. Albarracin, B.T. Johnson, & M.P. Zanna (Eds.), *The handbook of attitudes* (pp. 173–221). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum

Arora Sangeeta, Kaur Simarpreet (2018), 'Perceived Risk Dimensions & its Impact on Intention to Use E-banking Services: A Conceptual Study' *Journal of Commerce and Accounting Research*, Vol. 7, Issue 2, pp 18-27.

Badak Shubham, Kolte Vaibhav, Agrawal Mamta, Gupta Sonia (2023), 'Revolution of Digital Payments in India' *Journal of Mobile Computing, Communications & Mobile Networks*, Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp 29-37.

Bazgosha, G., Eizi, N., Nawaser, K., & Parhizgar, M. M. (2012), 'Technology of E-banking: Perspective of Costumers' Perceived Risk and Uncertainty' *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, Vol. 5, Issue 2, pp. 2200-2208.

Bhatnagar Puneett, Rajesh Anupama (2023), 'Neo banking Adoption- An Integrated UTAUT-3, Perceived Risk and Recommendation Model' *South Asian Journal of Marketing*.

Budhi Haryanto, Santosa Teguh, Setiyawati Sri (2022), 'Effects of Perceived Risk on the Intention to use Internet Banking by Implementing the Technology Acceptance Model' *International Journal of Economics & Business Issues*' Vol. 1, Issue 1.

Chandrasekaran S., Narayanan M (2019), 'Digital Payment in India'.

Chawla Deepak, Joshi Himanshu (2019), 'Consumer Attitude and Intention to Adopt Mobile Wallet in India- An Empirical Study' *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Vol. 37, Issue 7, pp.1590-1618.

Cunningham, L. F., Gerlach, J., & Harper, M. D. (2005), 'Perceived Risk and E-banking Services: An Analysis from the Perspective of the Consumer' *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, Vol. 10, Issue 2, pp. 165-178.

Dais Fred (1989), 'Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology' MIS Quarterly [Vol. 13, No. 3 \(Sep., 1989\)](#).

Dash, M., Mishra, B. B., Biswal, S. K., & Mishra, S. (2012). Understanding consumers' risks perception for banking on the Internet. International Journal of Engineering and Management Sciences, 3(2), 146-150.

Fadare, O. A. (2015). A survey on perceived risk and intention of adopting internet banking. The Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce, 21(1).

Farzianpour, F., Pishdar, M., Shakib, M. D., & Toloun, M. R. S. H. (2014). Consumers' perceived Risk and its effect on adoption of online banking services. American Journal of Applied Sciences, 11(1), 47.

Featherman, M. S., & Pavlou, P. A. (2003). Predicting e-services adoption: A perceived risk facets perspective. International Journal of Human-Computer Studies, 59(4), 451-474.

Hanafizadeh, P., & Khedmatgozar, H. R. (2012). The mediating role of the dimensions of the perceived risk in the effect of customers' awareness on the adoption of Internet banking in Iran. Electronic Commerce Research, 12(2), 151-175.

Haritha P.H. (2022), 'Mobile Payment Service Adoption: Understanding Customers for an Application of Emerging Financial Technology' Information and Computer Security, Vol. 31, Issue 2, pp. 145- 171.

Joshi Himanshu, Chawla Deepak (2024), 'Impact of Security on Wallet Adoption: Multiple and Serial Mediating Roles of Trust and Attitude and Gender as a Moderator' International Journal of Bank Marketing, Vol. 42, Issue 5, pp. 870-896.

Kesharwani, A., & Tripathy, T. (2012), 'Dimensionality of Perceived Risk and its Impact on Internet Banking Adoption: An Empirical Investigation' Services Marketing Quarterly, Vol. 33, Issue 2, 177-193.

Kesharwani, Ankit, & Singh Bisht, S. (2012), 'The Impact of Trust and Perceived Risk on Internet Banking Adoption in India: An extension of Technology Acceptance Model' International Journal of Bank Marketing, Vol. 30, Issue 4, pp. 303-322.

Khan Waseem Ahmad, Abideen Zain Ul (2023), 'Effects of behavioral intention on usage behavior of digital wallets: the mediating role of perceived risk and moderating role of Perceived Service Quality and Perceived Trust' Future Business Journal, Vol. 9, pp 1-15.

Kurian Jacob (2022), 'A Study on India's Digital Payments and their Impact on Consumers' International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, Vol. 10, Issue 4, pp. b17- b21.

L. Vimal Raj, Amilan S, Aparna K (2023), 'Factors Influencing the Adoption of Cashless Transactions: Towards a Unified View' South Asian Journal of Marketing, Vol. 5, Issue 1, pp. 74-90.

Lee, M. C. (2009). Factors influencing the adoption of internet banking: An integration of TAM and TPB with perceived risk and perceived benefit. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 8(3), 130-141.

Lifen Zhao, A., Hanmer-Lloyd, S., Ward, P., & Goode, M. M. (2008), 'Perceived Risk and Chinese Consumers' Internet Banking Services Adoption' *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Vol. 26, Issue 7, pp. 505-525.

Littler, D., & Melanthiou, D. (2006). Consumer perceptions of risk and uncertainty and the implications for behaviour towards innovative retail services: the case of internet banking. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 13(6), 431-443.

Manrai Rishi, Goel Utkarsh, Yadav Prashant Dev (2021), 'Factors Affecting Adoption of Digital Payments by Semi-Rural Indian Women: Extension of UTAUT-2 with Self Determination Theory & Perceived Credibility' *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 73, Issue 6, pp. 814-838.

Moradi, M., Ghomian, M. M., & Sarjanian, Z. (2012). Investigation of the effect of customers' perceived risk and uncertainty on the usage of the internet banking (A case study of Saderat Bank of Mashhad). *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 18(5), 617-623.

Pandey Shinki Katyayani (2022), 'A Study on Digital Payments System on Consumer Perception: An Empirical Survey' *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, Vol. 16, Issue 3, pp. 10121- 10131.

Rani Amita (2021), 'Digital Economy in India: Opportunities and Challenges' *Journal of Emerging Technologies & Innovative Research*, Vol. 8, Issue 2, pp 2367-2376.

Reepu, Arora Rakhi (2022), 'The Effect of Perceived Risk on Intention to Use Online Banking' *Universal Journal of Accounting and Finance*, Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp. 62-71.

Roy, S. K., Balaji, M. S., Kesharwani, A., & Sekhon, H. (2017). Predicting Internet banking adoption in India: a perceived risk perspective. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 25(5-6), 418-438.

Sandhu Kamaljeet, Dayanandan Ajit, Kunthuru Sudershan (2023), 'Fintech Innovation for Financial Inclusion: Can India Make it?' *International Journal of Accounting and Information Management*.

Shrivastava Deepak, Shrivastava Apurva, Prakash Gyan (2019), 'A Study on the Determining Demographic Factors for Green Banking Usage' *Think India Journal*, Vol. 22, Issue 14, pp 13979-13986.

Shrivastava Deepak, Shrivastava Apurva, Prakash Gyan (2019), 'Using Technology Acceptance Model to Study Customers' Perception Towards Green Banking' *Think India Journal*, Vol. 22, Issue 3, pp. 402-409.

Singh Ashish Kumar, Sharma Prayas (2023), 'A Study of Indian GenX and Millenials Consumers' Intention to Use Fintech Payment Services during COVID- 19 Pandemic' Journal of Modelling in Management, Vol. 18, Issue 4, pp. 1177-1203.

Sinha Neena, Paul Justin, Singh Nidhi (2024), 'Mobile Payments for Bottom of the Pyramid: Towards a Positive Social Change' Technological Forecasting and Social Change, Vol. 202.

Siraye, Z. (2014). Customers' adoption of electronic banking service channels in Ethiopia: An integration of technology acceptance model and perceived risk with theory of planned behaviour. International Journal of Electronic Finance, 8(1), 21-34.

Sivathanu Brijesh (2017), 'Adoption of Digital Payment Systems in the Era of Demonetization in India' Journal of Science & Technology Policy Management, Vol. 10, Issue 1, pp. 143- 171.

Sobti Neharika (2019), 'Impact of Demonetization on Diffusion of Mobile Payment Services in India Antecedents of Behavioural Intention and Adoption Using Extended UTAUT Model' Journal of Advances in Management Research, Vol. 16, Issue 4, pp. 472-497.

Trafimow, David. (2009). The Theory of Reasoned Action. Theory & Psychology - THEOR PSYCHOL. 19. 501-518.

Trafimow David (2009), 'User Acceptance of Information Technology: System Characteristics, User Perceptions and Behavioural Impacts' International Journal of Man- Machine Studies, Vol. 38, pp.475-487.

Undale Swapnil, Kulkarni Ashish, Patil Harshil (2021), 'Perceived e-wallet Security: Impact of COVID- 19 Pandemic' Vilakshan- XIMB Journal of Management, Vol. 18, Issue 1, pp. 89-104.

Vally K Suma, Divya K Hema (2018), 'A Study on Digital Payments in India with Perspective of Consumers' Adoption' International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, Vol. 119, Issue 5, pp. 1259-1267.

Venkatesh, V. and Davis, F.D. "A Model of the Antecedents of Perceived Ease of Use: Development and Test," Decision Sciences (27:3), 1996, 451-481

Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F.D. (2000). A Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal Field Studies. *Management Science*, 46, 186-204.

Viswanath Venkatesh, Fred D. Davis, (2000) A Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal Field Studies. *Management Science* 46(2):186-204.

Yadav Priyanka, Kumar Abhishek, Mishra Saroj Kumar, Kochhar Khyati (2024), 'Financial equality through Technology: Do Perceived Risks Deter Indian Women from Sustained Use of Mobile Payment Service?' International Journal of Information Management Data Insights, Vol. 4.